

Blockchain: An exploratory view on the use of blockchain as cybersecurity tool in remotely working environments

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ABSTRACT

Blockchain technology has gained more and more interest over the years and can be utilized in several different ways.

In this research we will explore how the application of blockchain technology can contribute to the cybersecurity within companies. By using blockchain to distribute sensitive company data to their employees, who are working from home, the security of this data can be improved.

Also, we will investigate whether employees are willing to support their company in using this technology, while working from home. By consulting literature, conducting interviews with experts in the field of blockchain and cybersecurity and conducting a survey among employees this research will contribute to the research field by providing insight in the possibilities of using blockchain technology to improve cybersecurity of companies.

Keywords

Blockchain Technology, Cybersecurity, Data Storage, Remote Work

INTRODUCTION

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, employees are obligated to work from home as much as possible. Recent studies state that 35.2 percent of the US workforce worked entirely from home in May 2020. In contrast, when the pandemic had not severely affected the USA in February 2020, only 8.2 percent of the workforce was working from home (Bick, Blandin & Mertens, 2020).

There are several consequences for companies and employees as a result of the new remote-working environment. Even though it can have a positive effect on the flexibility for employees, it can

also lead to reduced productivity (Bartik et al., 2020). Additionally, it can lead to consequences to the cybersecurity of companies and the safety of their data (Curran, 2020). While negative consequences are often the first that come to mind, the remote working situation could offer opportunities to contribute to cybersecurity as well. This paper focuses on the potential of running blockchain technology on the devices and networks of employees that are working from home to strengthen the cybersecurity of their employer.

It is estimated that after the pandemic the share of working days spent at home by full-time workers will be tripled compared to before the pandemic (Altig et al., 2020). If there is potential to strengthen cybersecurity using blockchain, the remote working situation could boost the implementation and adoption of this technology for security purposes. Especially if employees are willing to work predominantly from home on a permanent basis and if they are willing to use blockchain as a security measure. Companies could then start developing an ecosystem where they can use their employees working from home as nodes to utilize the strength of a distributed blockchain to store the companies' data and to validate transactions.

The goal of this paper is therefore to explore the potential of applying blockchain technology to improve cybersecurity within companies, focused on the remote-working environment.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Blockchain was introduced in 2008 and at this time it was only a peer-to-peer version of electronic cash which would allow online payments to be sent directly from one party to another without going through a financial institution (Nakamoto, 2008).

Ever since the introduction, the technology associated with bitcoin has been used in numerous different practice settings. Even more so, it has been the subject of a number of research papers. Research by Butijn et al. (2020) provides a complete definition of blockchain based on literature and

describes the current state of its applications and challenges. The extent to which blockchain is used is confirmed by Casino et al. (2019) in a literature review where they describe blockchain's potential in different business settings and across industries. Among other subjects, they encourage further research into the adoption of blockchain by companies and into the use of blockchain for security solutions. The current state of the use of blockchain in cybersecurity is described in a paper by Taylor et al. (2020), where they determine it is mainly used as supporting technology. Apart from its applications, Walsh et al. (2020) determined that there is still resistance by organizations to adopt blockchain. The resistance to adopt blockchain will only go away once the performance of blockchain is at the same level as contemporary technologies.

As blockchain is mainly used as supporting technology in cybersecurity and organizations are hesitant to adopt the new technology, it seems as if blockchain-driven cybersecurity is still in a conceptual phase. Since a key strength of blockchain is its decentralized nature (Casino et al., 2019) and the number of people working from home is historically high, this paper explores the potential of blockchain in cybersecurity in a remote working environment. More specifically, it explores if a more distributed network due to employees running part of a blockchain at home adds value to the cybersecurity of the company.

This knowledge gap led to the following research question:

“To what extent can the combination of people working from home and the use of blockchain technology within companies increase the security of company information?”

To help answer the research question the following sub-questions are formulated:

Theoretical research questions:

1. What is blockchain?
2. What is cybersecurity?
3. What are current developments and applications of blockchain in cybersecurity?
4. How can the users' attitude towards using a new technology be measured?

Practical research questions:

1. To what extent does blockchain have added value in cybersecurity of companies in the current situation of working remotely?

2. To what extent are employees willing to use blockchain for the cybersecurity of their employer in a remote-working environment?

THEORY

Blockchain

Blockchain was introduced in 2008 when Satoshi Nakamoto presented Bitcoin, a purely peer-to-peer version of electronic cash which would allow online payments to be sent directly from one party to another without going through a financial institution (Nakamoto, 2008). Since the introduction of Blockchain, the technology has been used for many different purposes and it has been researched extensively. Many researchers use different definitions for blockchain, which can lead to confusion. In a systematic literature review by Butijn et al. (2020), many of these definitions were analyzed. Based on this analysis, a complete definition was developed encompassing the most important characteristics of blockchain:

Blockchain technology is a form of distributed ledger, which is a record or book of transactions, technology deployed on a peer-to-peer network, which consists of nodes, where all data is replicated, shared, and synchronously spread across multiple peers. The technology allows actors participating in the network to perform, sign, and announce transactions by employing public key cryptography, where two pairs of keys are used to allow other actors to interact with one another; a private and public key. Transactions are executed following a consensus protocol operated by specific nodes to ensure the validity of transactions requested by other peers in the network, and to synchronize all shared copies of the distributed ledger. These nodes are the peers in the peer-to-peer network, the devices that are capable of processing and verifying transactions. During a consensus protocol execution, the data of valid transactions, along with other required metadata concerning the network, and the hash of the previous block is bundled into a block using hashing functions. Hashing is a method of calculating a relatively unique fixed-size output. The essential and key property reflecting blockchain technology architectures is that each block contains the hash of their predecessor, therefore linking all prior transactions to newly appended transactions; the blocks therefore form a

chain with the aim of establishing a tamper-proof historical record. (P.00:13)

This definition describes all components of blockchain and makes it more understandable. In this research, the distributed nature of blockchain, the ability to share transactions and portions of data and the validity of these data transactions are the central points of focus.

Cybersecurity

Similar to blockchain, cybersecurity has been researched extensively over the years and academia developed a number of definitions. Based on nine different definitions, Craigen, Diakun-Thibault and Purse (2014) compiled the following definition:

Cybersecurity is the organization and collection of resources, processes, and structures used to protect cyberspace and cyberspace-enabled systems from occurrences that misalign de jure from de facto property rights. (P.16)

This definition is derived from earlier definitions, their underlying themes and their critiques. It includes interactions between systems and humans that are organized to protect property rights within cyberspace (Craigen et al., 2014). The focus in this research lies on using blockchain as a resource within cybersecurity.

Applications of blockchain in cybersecurity

According to Taylor et al. (2020) research is conducted throughout a range of areas within information technology to investigate how blockchain can be used to improve cybersecurity. At this moment, blockchain is mainly used as supporting technology and is still in the conceptual phase. The three main areas in which research is conducted are the Internet of Things (IoT), network security and data storage & sharing. Whereas security within the IoT is the most researched area at this moment, not all companies use IoT in their daily operations. As most companies do have to deal with data in their daily operations, applications within network security and data security are more relevant.

Network security

Blockchain is mainly used as an extra security layer of a virtual network function within a network (Alvarenga, Rebello & Duarte, 2018). This relates to a virtual network where network functions such as a firewall or a router are replaced by blockchain technology (Clayman et al., 2014). This way a virtual network of scale can be created, without the

capital expenditure cost of having physical hardware (Yi et al., 2018). Other uses of blockchain in network security include using it as a security layer in a software-defined network (SDN) to block alien users from the network (Basnet & Shakya, 2017) and securing virtual machines used to facilitate cloud computing (Bozic, Pujolle & Secci, 2017).

Data storage & sharing

Blockchain is mainly used for data provenance within data and storage sharing, due to its tamper-proof historical record (Salman, 2018). An example is Prochain, which records all activities such as creation and deletion of files within a decentralized cloud storage (Liang, 2017). A similar concept is Blockstack, which detects any change in a storage system by checking the corresponding hash in the blockchain with the hash stored in the cloud (Ali, 2016). These applications increase the detection of malicious activities.

Attitude towards a new technology

The conceptual model is partly based on the technology acceptance model (TAM). This model is developed to construct a better understanding of the drivers of users' attitude towards the use of a type of technology (Davis, 1989). The model received significant validation over the years (Taherdoost, 2017) and is used to assess user's attitude towards the personal use of blockchain technology before (Gover et al., 2019). The main purpose of the TAM is however to analyze attitude towards a new technology in a business setting (Taherdoost, 2017). Technology acceptance models normally assume a voluntary setting of technology use. In a business environment implementation of a new technology is often mandated by senior management, limiting the possibility to explain the employees' attitude towards usage. However, the TAM does well in both environments (Hwang, Al-Arabiati & Shin, 2015).

The attitude towards using a technology can be assessed by analyzing the relationship between the perceived ease of use and the perceived usefulness of that technology. In theory, the perceived ease of use relates to the extent a user believes using a technology is free of effort, whereas the perceived usefulness relates to the extent a user believes using technology will enhance their work performance (Davis, 1989). In the model, perceived ease of use has a positive influence on attitude to use as well as on perceived usefulness. Perceived usefulness has a positive influence on attitude to use as well (Davis, 1989). As there is no widespread use of blockchain in cybersecurity in a remote-working environment, perceived ease of use relates in this research to guidance and training a user receives. Perceived usefulness relates to the belief that blockchain has a positive influence on cybersecurity and if the use is

necessary.

Conceptual model

Figure 1. Conceptual model

The conceptual model shows that using blockchain in a remote-working environment is investigated to analyze if it has an influence on the level of cybersecurity. Additionally, the attitude that employees have regarding the use of blockchain is investigated. If employees are willing to use blockchain technology, that might increase the potential of increased cybersecurity. Employee attitude towards using blockchain is estimated by perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Both measures are expected to have a positive relation on attitude towards blockchain.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses are formulated for the deductive part of this research. They aid in the better understanding of the relation between the usage of blockchain in a remote-working environment and the potential of increased cybersecurity.

H1: Attitude towards using blockchain as a cybersecurity measure increases if employees believe their company's cybersecurity needs to improve.

H2: Attitude towards using blockchain as a cybersecurity measure increases if the technology is easy to use.

H3: Perceived usefulness increases if employees feel the technology is easy to use

Methodology

Research Design

To incorporate multiple viewpoints, this research uses a mixed-method data collection approach. That means a combination of secondary data, qualitative and quantitative data is used. Qualitative data is used for the exploratory part of this research, where the focus lies on investigating if the application of blockchain technology could lead

to better cybersecurity when people are working remotely. Due to the exploratory nature of this part of the research, an inductive approach to theory development is used (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

Quantitative data is used to measure the perception of employees on using blockchain technology if imposed by their employer. The quantitative data is obtained by the use of an online survey. The use of quantitative data allows for generalization of the results and uses a deductive approach to theory development as it allows for generalizations of the results (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2016). Additionally, secondary data is used to get a better understanding about the research topic and to create a foundation for the qualitative data.

A pragmatic philosophy is taken into account, as multiple viewpoints from different perspectives are used to get a better understanding of the problem statement (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The research focuses on one point in time, making it cross-sectional.

Data collection and analysis

Secondary data

Secondary data is mainly derived from peer-reviewed journal articles and conference papers, taking their ranking and scientific impact in consideration. Scholarly books and governmental sources were used for background information.

Qualitative data

As knowledge about the application of blockchain in cybersecurity is possessed by a limited number of experts and the nature of the subject is complex, interviews were favored over focus groups. Judgement sampling was used to select participants based on their expertise in either blockchain, cybersecurity or a combination of both topics. Interviews were conducted with the following participants:

#	Name	Relevance
1	Paul Bessems	- CEO Weconomics - Helping companies to create an ecosystem to implement blockchain - Author of blockchain books
2	Alexander Remie	- Blockchain security engineer at Trail of Bits
3	Johan de Groot	- Head of Technology at LiveRamp - Providing data connectivity services using blockchain - CTO & Founder of Faktor - Acquired by LiveRamp

Figure 2. Interviewees

Open coding was used to put the data into thematic categories and to analyze matching and contradicting information.

There are factors limiting the reliability and

validity of the data derived from the interviews. First, saturation has not been achieved due to the limited number of participants interviewed for this research. This is caused by the limited time frame of the research and the small number of experts willing to participate. Second, not all data was relevant to the topic as interviewees sometimes drifted from the subject. Third, questions were modified based on the results of previous interviews to retrieve more relevant knowledge and to avoid drifting. These three factors limit the internal and external validity of the exploratory part of this research.

Quantitative data

The population was set to contain people who are or have been working from home due to the COVID-19 pandemic. To approach the population the sampling frame was set as the professional networks of the researchers through LinkedIn. A total of 1380 individual connections were reached by subtracting common connections from the total number of combined connections.

A total of 41 participants responded, resulting in a response rate of 2.97%. From the 41 responses, 5 had to be removed as the respondents did not work remotely. The data has been cleaned by removing responses from people who do not work at home, reducing the sample size from 41 to 36.

As perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness are abstract concepts, multi-item constructs were used to measure the variables. For perceived usefulness 4 survey questions were used and for perceived ease of use 5 questions, all on a 5-point Likert scale. As these questions were developed for the purpose of this research, internal validity is limited. The Cronbach's Alpha for these variables is 0.671 for perceived ease of use and 0.673 for perceived usefulness. They are considered reliable since they approach a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.7. The survey questions can be found in appendix A.

The external validity is moderate. The sampling frame approaches the population, but the sample size is not sufficient to allow for generalizability.

RESULTS

Transition to blockchain

Companies are currently experimenting with blockchain technology by setting up simulations and proof of concepts. Some sectors are setting up consortiums, which are project groups organized by several companies. If companies do want to transition to a fully decentralized database a new ecosystem must be created. Some companies are not fully implementing blockchain by transitioning to a

complete decentral environment, but rather add several small blockchain features to their central database. This means that companies need to develop a new organizational infrastructure. In addition, to successfully implement blockchain, the context and timing needs to be correct. Furthermore, the company must possess the required knowledge and organizational infrastructure (Bessems, personal communication, 2020).

Working from home

With the blockchain concept of data storage, individuals can offer their storage and hardware capacity in return for a reimbursement. A strong criterion for blockchain adoption is incentives. The stronger such incentive models are, the greater blockchains' success in the space can become, as this applies for data storage as well (Groot, personal communication, 2020).

Currently, companies are working on security by using new and better tools. A different approach could be to remove the motivation to hack or compromise information and data. In a specific block on the blockchain, information from different sources is stored. Even when a particular block is compromised, the data in these blocks are not valuable to hackers since there is no relation between these pieces of information. This can reduce the motivation for hacking or compromising company data compared to when it is stored on a centralized server (Bessems, personal communication, 2020).

The security of data in a blockchain depends partly on the number of validators (nodes) in a network. The more nodes in a network, the more secure the network tends to be. Nodes can be companies, but also people who work remotely from home (Bessems, personal communication, 2020). Employees will be made more responsible for company data and possibly increasing company engagement, whilst obtaining incentives to do so (Groot, personal communication, 2020). The drawback here is that companies need to increase their trust in employees, since valuable data will be stored in the employee's private environment.

An important annotation to make, is that blockchain technology has increased its scalability compared to the start in 2008 with the Bitcoin blockchain. But most of these infrastructures are still not scalable enough to handle many transactions per second, which might be required for some business processes nowadays (Groot, personal communication, 2020). Another risk might be that even though blockchain technology seems secure now due to its encryption, new technologies like quantum computing might be able to subvert this in the future (Remie, personal communication, 2020).

Some of the benefits of running a blockchain node from home, is when a hacker conducts a DDOS attack, they have to attack all nodes at the same time, which is harder than attacking a single company, which has a single point of failure (Remie, personal communication, 2020). If one node is compromised, other nodes will still detain all the information that was initially stored (Groot, personal communication, 2020).

A suitable option could be that employers equip their employees with a device that is pre-installed with a blockchain node such as a Raspberry Pi, a small computer, which takes the slightest amount of effort and training for employees to adapt this technology, in order to contribute to the cybersecurity of companies (Remie, personal communication, 2020). To increase adoption of such concepts, a plug-and-play design is most suitable, in order to reduce difficulties for employees to use this technology. Companies will have to arrange these facilities accordingly (Groot, personal communication, 2020). The drawback of this concept however, is that companies have to invest in hardware, while most companies are following the current trend of moving in the opposite direction, by shifting to cloud environments (Groot, personal communication, 2020).

In the ideal situation, a combination of companies and individuals is desired to run blockchain nodes in the future. Although these nodes might not secure specific information, instead all nodes combined secure the entire network, validating transactions from a wide range of companies or individuals (Bessemers, personal communication, 2020).

Employees' attitude towards using blockchain

Based on the answers of 36 employees who are currently working remotely, it can be concluded that employees are willing to use blockchain to increase the cybersecurity of their company. The mean score of the employees' attitude towards using blockchain was 4.03 out of 5. Additionally, the consensus was high among employees, as the standard deviation of the answers was only 0.696.

Perceived usefulness

Perceived usefulness has a positive linear relation to the employees' attitude to use blockchain as a security measure, with a correlation coefficient of 0.389. While the correlation is small, employees do generally feel that working remotely can lead to reduced cybersecurity (mean of 3.97). Additionally, they feel that additional security measures have to be taken in the current remote-work situation (mean of 3.58).

Perceived ease of use

Perceived ease of use has a positive linear relation to the employees' attitude to use blockchain as a security measure, with a correlation coefficient of 0.660. The correlation is moderate to strong, and indicates that ease of use is the most important factor that determines if an employee is willing to use blockchain. Ease of use has a small correlation with perceived usefulness, with a correlation coefficient of 0.330. This indicates if the technology is easy to use, it could lead to increased perceived usefulness.

It is also clear that employees prefer to use it on their work computer (mean of 4.17) compared to their personal computer (mean of 3.08). Additionally, they seem more favorable towards an easy-to-use device (mean of 4.28) than if they need to follow an extensive training (mean of 2.97).

DISCUSSION

Blockchain technology is used in a range of industries and for a variety of purposes. One of these purposes is cybersecurity, in which blockchain knows many applications. It can be used as an encryption technology for data or to replace already existing elements in a virtual environment. In general, the technology is not used as the key component of the cybersecurity framework. Instead, its main purpose is to serve as a supporting technology.

This research shows however that blockchain has more to offer within cybersecurity than merely acting in a supporting role. Since a blockchain can become more secure once it is more distributed, the remote-working environment could accelerate the use of blockchain as a cybersecurity measure. A server that contains company data is often centralized in a physical location or in a cloud. If that server would be divided into nodes running at the homes of employees, the blockchain network would be more decentralized and therefore more secure. The main benefits are that the motivation for attacking a server is reduced, due to its decentralized nature. Additionally, the company's data remains secure if one block is compromised and that every data change is recorded.

The data shows that employees have a positive attitude towards the use of blockchain as a cybersecurity measure for their company. However, it also shows that employees are less positive to follow extensive training on how to use it. Additionally, it is argued that the effort for employees to use it should be low and that there might be a need for monetary incentives. It is clear however that the best way to implement a decentralized data network is to have a plug-and-play device that is easy to use.

There are important considerations that limit

the potential of using blockchain as a cybersecurity in a remote-working environment. Companies need to adapt their business model to create an ecosystem in which they can fully implement a decentralized server. This has a high entry barrier and could have high implementation cost. Additionally, blockchain does not have the transaction rate yet to be utilized for major data storage and sharing.

This implies that the concept of using blockchain in cybersecurity in a remote-working environment has great potential, but that the technology is not sufficiently developed to implement it. Nevertheless, the current situation of remote working could be an accelerator for the development and adoption of blockchain in cybersecurity.

CONCLUSION

The research paper provides an answer to the given research question: “To what extent can the combination of people working from home and the use of blockchain technology within companies increase the security of company information?”

From the research, it can be concluded that the use of blockchain technology can be of added value to the cybersecurity of a company. By facilitating a pre-installed device that runs a blockchain node, company data can be secured by these nodes in private environments of employees. Based on the conducted survey, the majority of employees are willing to use this technology, given that least effort has to be made in order to use this technology. Therefore, this research shows that there is sufficient willingness to use blockchain technology among employees.

This research has given insights in the willingness of employees to use blockchain technology to increase company security and what possible applications blockchain technology might have in increasing cybersecurity of companies. Whereas ensuring company growth is often the main priority of managers, keeping up with emerging technologies and improving cybersecurity to ensure data safety is an important focus area as well. Therefore, this research aims at delivering insights in improving cybersecurity by using new technologies like blockchain, contributing to the managerial relevance of this research.

While there is sufficient research into the application of blockchain in cybersecurity as a supporting technology, this research went further to investigate blockchain as the main technology in cybersecurity. Additionally, it puts the use of blockchain in the new context of working from home. This new context allows for future research implications, such as the possibilities of implementation of plug-and-play nodes and the

feasibility of creating an ecosystem in which this application of blockchain technology can be used.

This knowledge will have a contribution to both academics and managers. However, a remark has to be made. Because this qualitative research was done on a relatively small scale, the findings will not be generalizable to a broader population. Additionally, the limited sample size of the quantitative research requires additional research to support the results.

The changed circumstances due to COVID-19, has forced people to work remotely. Applying blockchain technology in these new circumstances can have great benefits as shown in this research, whereas this research can be used to build further upon exploring how blockchain can be applied in certain cybersecurity processes.

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Appendix A - Survey questions

Blockchain is most known for being the technology behind the electronic valuta BitCoin. The technology of Blockchain can however also be used for other purposes, such as the improvement of cybersecurity.

With the increased focus on working from home, the security level of a company's data or network could be reduced. While Blockchain technology could be used to improve the security, this can have implications for the employee. You might have to take extra steps to connect to your network, you might need to get specific training, you might need to store part of the blockchain technology on your personal computer or you might need to plug in a small device.

Therefore, we are researching the willingness of employees who work remotely to use Blockchain technology to improve their company's security level. Please note that to answer this survey, you do not need to have any prior knowledge about Blockchain.

Thank you for taking the time to fill out this survey.

1. I am or have been working from home

Yes/No

2. Before this survey, I was already familiar with blockchain technology

Strongly disagree / disagree / neutral / agree / strongly agree

Purpose

3. I feel that working remotely can lead to a lower security level of my companies' data

Strongly disagree / disagree / neutral / agree / strongly agree

4. My company communicated that working remotely could lead to a decreased level of security

Strongly disagree / disagree / neutral / agree / strongly agree

5. I feel that extra security measures have to be taken in order to increase my companies' cybersecurity

Strongly disagree / disagree / neutral / agree / strongly agree

6. I feel that if my employer implements a new technology such as Blockchain to increase the level of cybersecurity, it will be beneficial for my company.

Strongly disagree / disagree / neutral / agree / strongly agree

Ease of use

7. I would be willing to use blockchain technology to increase the cybersecurity of my company, if I need to use my private computer for it

Strongly disagree / disagree / neutral / agree / strongly agree

8. I would be willing to use blockchain technology to increase the cybersecurity of my company, if I need to use my work computer for it

Strongly disagree / disagree / neutral / agree / strongly agree

9. I would be willing to use blockchain technology if my employer provides an installed device, which means I do not have to install or actively use the technology myself

Strongly disagree / disagree / neutral / agree / strongly agree

10. I would be willing to use blockchain technology if that means that I need to spend a working day on reading an instruction manual provided by my employer

Strongly disagree / disagree / neutral / agree / strongly agree

11. I would be willing to use blockchain technology if that means that I need to follow an extensive training program (1 or 2 days) to use the technology

Strongly disagree / disagree / neutral / agree / strongly agree

Final Question / Control Question

12. I would be willing to use blockchain technology as a measure to increase my company's cybersecurity level

Strongly disagree / disagree / neutral / agree / strongly agree

Appendix B – SPSS outputs

Independent variables means

	Report										
	2. Before this survey, I was already familiar with blockchain technology	3. I feel that working remotely can lead to a lower security level of my company's data	4. My company communicated that working remotely could lead to a decreased level of security	5. I feel that extra security measures have to be taken in order to increase my companies' cybersecurity	6. I feel that if my employer implements a new technology such as Blockchain to increase the level of cyber security, it will be beneficial for my company	7. I would be willing to use blockchain technology to increase the cybersecurity of my company, if I need to use my private computer for it	8. I would be willing to use blockchain technology to increase the cybersecurity of my company, if I need to use my work computer for it	9. I would be willing to use blockchain technology if my employer provides an installed device, which means I do not have to install or actively use the technology myself	10. I would be willing to use blockchain technology if that means that I need to spend a working day on reading an instruction manual provided by my employer	11. I would be willing to use blockchain technology if that means that I need to follow an extensive training program (1 or 2 days) to use the technology	12. I would be willing to use blockchain technology as a measure to increase my company's cyber security level
Mean	3,14	3,97	2,61	3,58	3,72	3,08	4,17	4,28	3,33	2,97	4,03
N	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	36
Std. Deviation	1,199	,878	1,225	1,025	,849	1,228	,845	,741	1,265	1,134	,696

Correlations

		12. I would be willing to use blockchain technology as a measure to increase my company's cyber security level	Purpose	EaseOfUse
12. I would be willing to use blockchain technology as a measure to increase my company's cyber security level	Pearson Correlation	1	.389*	.660**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.019	.000
	N	36	36	36
Purpose	Pearson Correlation	.389*	1	.330*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.019		.049
	N	36	36	36
EaseOfUse	Pearson Correlation	.660**	.330*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.049	
	N	36	36	36

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Cronbach's Alpha Purpose

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.673	4

Cronbach's Alpha Willingness

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
,671	5